

JANUS GRAPHENE NON-WOVEN FABRICS FOR ULTRALIGHT ELECTROMAGNETIC INTERFERENCE SHIELDING

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Keywords: Janus, Graphene non-woven fabrics, Hierarchical, Ultralight, EMI shielding

ABSTRACT

Sever electromagnetic interference (EMI) pollutions have been resulted from the widespread modern electronics and communications, making the development of EMI shielding materials an urgent demand for minimizing hazards of unwanted electromagnetic waves. In this study, Janus graphene non-woven fabrics (NWFs) are prepared for exceptional EMI shielding. Janus graphene NWFs exhibit a two-layer structure, the film layer caused by the suddenly pressure difference under vacuum filtration through a filter and the NWFs layer consisting of interfused, continuous graphene fiber networks. The highly conductive graphene fiber skeleton and the continuous interfused network give rise to high electrical conductivities of ~ 5 S/cm, which are comparable with the chemical vapor deposition grown, no-defect graphene foam. Remarkable EMI shielding effectiveness (SE), with a highest of 83 dB, are delivered by the Janus graphene NWFs at a thickness of 1.1 mm. Thanks to the ultralow densities and small thickness, the Janus graphene NWFs exhibit exceptional specific SEs (SSEs) in the range of 1296-2098 dB·cm³/g and 18729-23147 dB·cm²/g, when normalized by volume and area densities, respectively.

1 INTRODUCTION

Rapid growth of severe electromagnetic pollutions resulted from the fast-developing and extensive use of electronics and communications has inevitably generated more and more detriments to the health of human beings and the normal operation of electronics. Therefore, it is urgent to develop effective electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding materials to reduce the harms of EMI pollutions in environments to human health and electronics. Large EMI shielding effectiveness (SE) values and lightweight are key parameters for applications in certain fields, such as automobiles, aircraft, aerospace and portable devices. The development of porous structures and the application of polymer-based composites reinforced with highly electrically conductive additives, such as graphene and carbon nanotubes (CNTs), are two effective strategies for the fabrication of lightweight EMI shielding materials [1-3]. The construction of porous structures reduces densities of materials and contributes to the enhancement of EMI shielding properties via improving multiple reflection of incident electromagnetic waves in the internals. The application of highly conductive fillers improves electrical conductivities of composites, leading to increased interactions between shielding materials and electromagnetic radiations.

Among different porous materials, foams and aerogels constructed by highly conductive nano-carbon materials and corresponding porous composites are most promising for EMI shielding because of their large electron mobilities, large specific areas, and excellent electrical conductivities. Conductive polymer composites have attracted much attention in recent years for lightweight EMI shielding because of their high electrical conductivities, low densities, and porous structures. Both excellent EMI SE and specific SE (SSE, SE normalized by volumetric density) values are reported for polymer-based aerogels and foams with graphene and CNT additives. An exceptional EMI SE of 75

dB and a large SSE of $\sim 833 \text{ dB}\cdot\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$ were obtained by graphene foam/CNT/ polydimethylsiloxane composites with densities of $\sim 0.09 \text{ g/cm}^3$ [4]. The ultralight multiwall CNT/waterborne polyurethane aerogels with a density of 0.11 g/cm^3 exhibited a good EMI SE value of $\sim 50 \text{ dB}$ [5]. Generally, conductive polymer foams can achieve good EMI SEs in the range of 20-80 dB, but their moderate densities result in limited SSE values. A SE of 40 dB was exhibited by commercial carbon foams [6]. A EMI SE of $\sim 85 \text{ dB}$ was achieved by Multiwall CNTs decorated carbon foams with a density of 0.5 g/cm^3 [7]. Currently, the development of ultra-lightweight carbon materials with high EMI shielding properties are promising and need to be explored.

In order to develop EMI shielding materials with lightweight, high electrical conductivities, and exceptional shielding properties, Janus graphene NWFs are produced using GO fiber precursors. After swelling with ethanol, GO fibers are inter-fused during the drying process, obtaining a three-dimensionally (3D) continuous graphene network. The graphene macro-assembly exhibit low density of around 40 mg/cm^3 and high electrical conductivities of 5 S/cm . Exceptional EMI SEs up to 70 dB are achieved by Janus graphene NWFs.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 preparation of Janus graphene NWFs

Graphene NWFs were fabricated by utilizing the self-interfusion characteristics [8] of graphene oxide (GO) fibers which were prepared via a wet-spinning method. Typically, the GO/N,N'-dimethyl formamide dispersions were wet-spun into ethyl acetate followed by drying and continuous collecting. After heating at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h for partial reduction of GO and removal of residual solvents, the GO fibers were cut by a shear mixer at a speed of 10k round per minute in ethanol. Janus GO NWFs were obtained by vacuum filtration of the GO short fibers through a membrane filter (47 mm in diameter, $0.2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in pore size). To prepare GO NWFs, the fiber fragments were collected using nylon meshes and vacuum filtrated. The Janus graphene NWFs and graphene NWFs were obtained after reducing the Janus GO NWFs and GO NWFs at $1600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h.

2.2 Characterization

Morphologies of graphene NWFs and Janus graphene NWFs were observed by scanning electron microscope (SEM, Hitachi S4800). Images of fragmental GO fibers were taken by a camera, followed by analyses using the software ImageJ to measure the length and diameter distributions. Densities of NWFs were obtained by the ratio of mass and volume. The scattering parameter, S_{11} and S_{21} , in the range of 8.2-12.4 GHz were measured by waveguide transmission line method by a vector network analyzer (Agilent Technologies N5230A). The reflective coefficient (R), the transmission coefficient (T), and the absorption coefficient (A) can be calculated using eqs 1-3 [9]:

$$R = |S_{11}|^2 \quad (1)$$

$$T = |S_{21}|^2 \quad (2)$$

$$A = 1 - R - T \quad (3)$$

The EMI SEs attributed to reflection (SE_A), absorption (SE_R) and the total SE (SE_T) of NWFs are obtained by eqs 4-6 [10]:

$$SE_A(\text{dB}) = -10 \log \left[\frac{|S_{21}|^2}{(1 - |S_{11}|^2)} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$SE_R(\text{dB}) = -10 \log (1 - |S_{11}|^2) \quad (5)$$

$$SE_T(dB) = SE_A + SE_R \quad (6)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphologies of Janus graphene NWFs

The continuous GO fibers fabricated by wet-spinning method were re-dispersed in ethanol, followed by cutting into short fibers, as shown in Figure 1a. Lengths of short GO fibers were mainly distributed in the range of 0.2-1.4 mm, obtaining an average length of 1.0 mm. After the NWFs were thermally reduced, diameters of the graphene fiber skeleton were mainly distributed among 14-20 μm with an average value of 16.8 μm .

Figure 1. (a) Image of short GO fibers taken by a camera; (b) length distribution of GO fibers; and (c) diameter distribution of graphene fiber skeleton after reduction.

Different NWF structures were obtained by adjusting the vacuum filtration process. When using a Nylon fabric to collect the short GO fiber dispersed in ethanol before filtration, isotropic NWFs were obtained. However, Janus graphene NWFs were fabricated when filtrating the short fiber/ethanol dispersions directly through a membrane. The Janus graphene NWFs exhibited a two-layer structure, the film layer caused by the suddenly pressure difference under vacuum filtration through a filter and the NWFs layer consisting of interfused, continuous graphene fiber networks (Figures 2a-c). Embedded graphene fibers were observed in the film layer, as shown in Figure 2c. The two layers were strongly interconnected, with fibers embedded in and interfused with the thin film layers, as shown in Figure 2d. After reduction, porous structures were formed within graphene fibers (Figures 2e,f), resulting in a hierarchical structure of Janus graphene NWFs. The GO fiber skeletons of NWF structures were consisted of stacking single-layer GO sheets. During thermal reduction, gasses were generated and released from the fibers. Porous structures were formed within the fibrous skeleton (Figures 2e,f), attributing to the high aspect ratio of graphene blocks and the large amount of gas releasing. As a result, hierarchical structure of Janus graphene NWFs were obtained.

Figure 2. (a) The photograph of Janus graphene MWFs; SEM images of (b) the NWF side, (c) the film side, (d) the interfacial connections of two sides, and (e,f) cross-sections of porous graphene fiber skeletons

3.2 Electrical and EMI shielding properties

The reflection (SE_R), absorption (SE_A) and multiple reflection of electromagnetic waves are responsible for EMI shielding [11]. The reflection of incident waves is dependent on interactions between electromagnetic waves and free charges on materials surfaces [12]. Higher electrical conductivities and larger free charge carrier densities generally result in higher SE_R values. The absorption of waves is determined by the ability of EMI shielding materials to attenuate EM radiations to internal and thermal energies [13]. Therefore, higher electrical and thermal conductivities, stronger polarizations under electromagnetic radiations, and other processes that promote energy consumption and dissipation contribute to higher SE_A . When the SE_T is larger than 10 dB, multiple-reflected waves are further absorbed, making contributions to the SE_A values.

Thanks to the hierarchical structure consisting of pores of the fabric structure in the range of dozens to around 200 μm and pores in the fibrous skeletons in the range of a few hundred nanometers to several microns. The hierarchical porous structure contributed to ultra-low densities of graphene NWFs and Janus NWFs of around 70 and 40 g/cm^3 , respectively, as shown in Figure 3a. During vacuum filtration, the formation of film layers in Janus NWFs significantly reduced pressure gradients from the air to the top of film layers, resulting in looser fabric structures and lower densities of Janus

NWFs. Accordingly, electrical conductivities of graphene NWFs and Janus NWFs of around 10 and 5 S/cm, respectively, regardless of the mass of GO fiber precursors (Figure 3b). Different thicknesses were resulted by varying mass of GO fiber precursors, while densities of the graphene NWFs or the Janus graphene NWFs remained stable.

Figure 3. (a) Densities and (b) electrical conductivities of graphene NWFs and Janus NWFs; EMI SEs of (c) Janus graphene NWFs and (d) graphene NWFs; SE_A and SE_R values of (e) Janus graphene NWFs and (f) graphene NWFs.

The EMI shielding properties of NWFs and Janus NWFs with different mass of GO precursors, or thicknesses, are shown in Figures 3c-f. The total SEs of both NWFs and Janus NWFs were enhanced gradually with the increasing mass of GO fiber precursors, or the increasing thicknesses. For Janus graphene NWFs fabricated by 120 mg GO short fibers, SEs value of ~80 dB were obtained at a thickness of 1.1 mm. As a comparison, 120 mg GO short fibers resulted in 0.55 mm graphene NWFs because of higher densities. Corresponding EMI SEs were 65 dB. According to previous studies, EMI

SE values of materials are highly dependent on electrical conductivities. However, higher SEs were achieved by Janus graphene NWF with lower electrical conductivities. This is mainly because of the effective wave reflection by film layer in Janus NWFs, the larger thickness, and the hierarchical porous structure of Janus graphene NWFs. Owing to the ultralow densities of $\sim 40 \text{ mg/cm}^3$, the Janus graphene NWFs achieved exceptional EMI SSEs (Figure 4). Extremely high SSEs up to 2098 $\text{dB}\cdot\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$, and 23147 $\text{dB}\cdot\text{cm}^2/\text{g}$ were obtained when normalized by volumetric and area densities, respectively.

Figure 4. Summary of specific EMI SEs of graphene NWFs and Janus NWFs.

4. CONCLUSION

A facial and novel approach was developed for the fabrication of hierarchical, lightweight Janus graphene NWFs by utilizing the self-infusion phenomenon of GO fibers. High electrical conductivities and excellent EMI shielding properties were achieved. Conclusions are summarized according to experimental studies, as listed in the following:

(i) Two-layer Janus graphene NWFs consisted of the film layer obtained by large sudden pressure difference during vacuum filtration process and the NWF layer exhibiting a fabric morphology. Porous structures were obtained within the graphene fiber skeleton, contributing to hierarchical porous structures of the Janus graphene NWFs.

(ii) Thanks to the three-dimensionally interconnected network, the highly electrically conductive graphene building blocks, and the hierarchical porous structure, graphene NWFs delivered ultralow densities of 40 mg/cm^3 and high electrical conductivities of 5 S/cm .

(iii) Exceptional EMI SEs, SSEs and SEs normalized by area densities up to 75 dB , $2098 \text{ dB}\cdot\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$, and $23147 \text{ dB}\cdot\text{cm}^2/\text{g}$, respectively, were achieved by Janus graphene NWFs in this study. The good electrical conductivities, the hierarchical porous structure, and the Janus morphology consisting of film layer and NWF layer mainly contributed to the absorption-dominated EMI shielding of Janus graphene NWFs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project was financially supported by the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (FRF-TP-18-002A1) and the China Postdoctoral Science Foundation (2018M641191). Technical assistance from the University of Science and Technology and Zhejiang University are also appreciated.

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